

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the pedagogical strategies for developing students' professional competence in higher education. It underscores the impact of modern teaching methods, interactive learning technologies, and integrating theory with practice to cultivate essential skills in future specialists. The study demonstrates the value of learner-centered approaches, critical thinking, and problem-solving tasks in equipping students for professional demands. Additionally, the paper stresses the ongoing need to update educational programs to address labor market needs and enhance the standard of professional training.*

Keywords: *professional competence; pedagogical aspects; higher education; student development; modern teaching methods; interactive learning; theory and practice integration; labor market requirements.*

Introduction

Professional competence is not conceptualized by a specialist merely as the acquisition of discrete knowledge and skills, but rather as the mastery of integrated knowledge and actions for each independent field of activity. Furthermore, competence necessitates the continuous enrichment of specialized knowledge, the learning of new information, the ability to comprehend significant social demands, and the capacity to seek out new knowledge, process it, and apply it effectively in one's practice.

Professional competence is most clearly manifested in the following situations. A specialist possessing professional competence:

- Systematically enriches their knowledge;
- Assimilates new information;
- Deeply understands the demands of the era;
- Actively seeks out new knowledge;
- Processes it and applies it effectively in their practical activities, specifically in:
 - ✓ Complex processes;
 - ✓ The execution of ambiguous tasks;
 - ✓ The utilization of contradictory information;
 - ✓ The ability to formulate a plan of action in unforeseen situations.

Thus, professional competence is the acquisition of the knowledge, skills, and qualifications necessary for a specialist to carry out professional activities, coupled with the ability to apply them at a high level in practice.

Part II: The Qualities of Professional Competence. The following qualities form the foundation of professional competence. (Part 1):

Below is a brief explanation of the essence of the qualities reflected in the foundation of professional competence.

1. **Social Competence** – The possession of skills and qualifications for demonstrating active engagement in social relations; the ability to engage in communication with subjects in professional activities.

2. **Special Competence** – This entails preparedness to organize professional-pedagogical activities, the rational resolution of professional-pedagogical tasks, the realistic assessment of one's performance results, and the consistent development of one's professional skills. This type of competence is underpinned by psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative, and communicative competences, which encompass the following meanings:

a) **Psychological Competence** – The ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, organize positive communication with students and other participants in the educational process, and to promptly recognize and resolve various negative psychological conflicts.

b) **Methodological Competence** – The rational methodological organization of the pedagogical process; the correct selection of forms for educational or instructional activities; the ability to choose methods and tools appropriate to the goal; the effective application of methods and the successful use of tools.

c) **Informational Competence** – The ability to search for, collect, sort, process, and utilize necessary, important, relevant, and useful information from the information environment in a purposeful, appropriate, and effective manner.

d) **Creative Competence** – A critical and creative approach to pedagogical activity; the ability to demonstrate one's creative abilities.

e) **Innovative Competence** – The ability to propose new ideas aimed at improving the pedagogical process, enhancing the quality of education, and increasing the effectiveness of the instructional process, and to implement them successfully in practice.

f) **Communicative Competence** – The ability to engage in sincere communication with all participants in the educational process, including students; to listen to them effectively; and to exert a positive influence on them.

g) **Personal Competence** – The achievement of consistent professional growth, the continuous improvement of one's qualification level, and the demonstration of one's internal potential in professional activities.

h) **Technological Competence** – The mastery of advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical skills; the ability to utilize modern tools, equipment, and technologies.

i) **Crisis Competence** – The ability to make rational decisions and act appropriately in emergency situations (e.g., natural disasters, technological failures) and when pedagogical conflicts arise.

A number of studies have directly investigated the specific professional competence inherent to teachers and its distinctive aspects. Among such research, one can include the inquiries conducted by A.K. Markova and B. Nazarova.

In her research, A.K. Markova notes that a teacher's professional competence consists of the following foundational components (see Figure 2).

Within the context of Uzbekistan, the specific professional competence unique to teachers and its distinctive aspects have also been studied. Among these studies, the research conducted by B. Nazarova holds particular significance. According to the researcher, the professional competence specific to a teacher is structured upon the following foundational components (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Key Foundational Components of Pedagogical Competence (according to B. Nazarova)

III. Developing a Teacher's Professional Competence

In achieving professional (including pedagogical) competence, self-directed work and self-development are of paramount importance. The tasks for self-development are identified through self-analysis and self-assessment.

For teachers to work on themselves consistently and effectively, adopting a project-based approach to their activities is beneficial. It is advisable for them to form the following model based on project-based planning. The model outlines the stages of self-development and the tasks to be implemented at each stage. The successful completion of tasks designated for each stage enables progression to the next. Once the tasks of a certain stage are completed, the teacher records this status in a separate section (see Table 1).

Furthermore, the "problem-based situation" serves as a means of reflecting problematicity in the form of a set of tasks. In the course of their activities, students consider and analyze specific situations and conditions when resolving contradictory situations.

Another scholar, A. Matyushkin, understands a problem-based situation as the following states. Specifically, he states that it is characterized by activity aimed at problem-solving in the cognitive processes interconnecting students and the factors influencing them. In this case, the student attempts to solve a specific existing problem, strives to find methods, and carries out related activities to derive knowledge.

In essence, problem-based situations have their own characteristics and differ from one another based on the following specific parameters: they can be distinguished by the method of activity, by its development, by levels, and by intellectual abilities. Alongside the concept of a "problem-based situation," the concept of an "educational problem" is also important, as it implements the principle of problematicity in education. The educational problem reflects the subjective characteristics of the problem being solved, creates a state of intellectual difficulty, and generates a problem-based situation.

Thus, M.I. Makhmutov, examining educational problems, identifies some important characteristics within them: the manifestation of problems; the form of problems; the content of problems; and the method of studying problems.

Another prominent scholar, D. Elkonin, emphasizes that problem-based educational problems have their own specific character in their resolution. He stresses the need to pay great attention to the specific features of the approaches in studying their methods, goals and objectives, content, and essence. He places significant emphasis on the non-repetitive nature of problems in problem-based education. To understand them, he says we must focus not only on changes in the subject itself but also on changes in the objects.

M. Makhmutov additionally highlights the key concepts of problem-based teaching.

Through problem-based educational technology alongside teachers, students develop their thinking. They strive to achieve desired results through various methods and means. This significantly contributes to broadening their perspectives. The main goal of problem-based educational technology is not merely for students to acquire knowledge from specific subjects, but to create analytically thinking subjects through mastering knowledge related to the sciences.

In higher education institutions, the effective use of problem-based teaching technologies in the philosophy course is related to the specific subject area used for developing analytical thinking, implemented on the basis of pedagogical design. In this scientific research, the mentioned problem is analyzed comprehensively, aiming to determine its place and role in the socio-humanitarian education fields.

According to the teachings of the renowned scholar A. Nikiforov, through mastering philosophy, an individual can possess culture and knowledge. It can show us true existence, because philosophy allows the student, along with isolated proofs of reality, to abstract and generalize holistic information about the world surrounding us in any sphere of life activity through analytical thinking, reaching a higher level, and enables the derivation of principles of the existence of the world surrounding humans beyond its application. From this, we can conclude that every qualified specialist contributes significantly to perfection not only as a specialist but also as humane individuals.

The pragmatic approach to determining the content aspects of education leaves very little room for expanding the teaching of philosophical disciplines. However, it must be specifically

emphasized that specialists have identified additional functions of philosophy that assist in perfecting virtues, which are an important factor for any field specialist. In particular, the critical and predictive functions determine the importance of philosophy for understanding and solving the crisis phenomena of our time and global problems. The critical function examines processes, events, and phenomena occurring in the world from the standpoint of a valuable approach, normative concepts, and an external vantage point developed in philosophy. Analytical thinking is considered crucial in actions aimed at improving and correctly directing events occurring in society. The predictive function directs society's attention to natural, social, or technical threats to people and contributes to creating a scientifically based prognosis (scenario) for the future.

In providing philosophical education to students, we are developing their ability to think analytically by using effective methods far from standard tests or samples. Today, the improvement and development of students' knowledge related to information culture depends on the progress of information and communication fields, which in turn is considered organically related to the problem of thinking culture. Philosophy is considered important in comprehensively studying this presented problem, i.e., it systematically analyzes the problems of societal development.

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